

Village Tourism as a Catalyst for Economic Prosperity: A Case Study of Pasawahan Village, Indonesia

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Abstract

Implementing the DesaWisata (Tourism Village) pilot program initiated by the Governor of West Java faces several challenges, particularly in Pasawahan Village. This study employs a qualitative-descriptive approach with purposive sampling for informant selection. The findings indicate that the implementation of the DesaWisata program is hindered by various issues, such as insufficient mentoring and socialization efforts by both local government and private sector, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of promotion and community interest in participating in tourism management. Therefore, enhancing the empowerment of managers and the community through more intensive socialization and mentoring is necessary to boost the local economy.

Keywords:

Tourism Village, Local Economy, Tourism Management.

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INTRODUCTION

Tourism has become an important pillar for many countries, including Indonesia, in attracting foreign trade and supporting monetary development. This sector plays an important role in reducing unemployment and expanding employment opportunities and significantly supports local government efforts. Tourism also creates new employment fields, preventing rural people from moving to big cities to find jobs, better education, and better medical services, abandoning their houses and lands. (Gao and Wu 2017)

In Indonesia, the tourism industry has been identified as one of the largest industry groups, accounting for around 8% of global exports of goods and services (Idajati&Andastry, 2017). The tourism sector holds a strategic position in economic development (Patience & Ifeanyi, 2022); with its increasingly important role in expanding trade and foreign investment (Idajati&Andastry, 2017). All of the benefits of a tourism village can be achieved by improving the quality and quantity of tourist attractions and the environmental quality of the settlements (Sesotyanningtyas and Manaf 2015).

Ecotourism is a new type of tourism that is being developed in Indonesia, despite introduced internationally in October 1999 by the World Tourism Organization (WTO) and has issued as encouragement for the countries in the world to develop sustainable tourism (Vitasurya 2016). Tourism potential has spread to several villages in Garut Regency, and as many as 131 Pioneer Tourism Villages have been formed in Garut Regency which is an implementation of the West Java Provincial Regulation Number 2 of 2022 concerning Tourism Villages. TarogongKaler District has 7 Pioneer Tourism Villages or the most with the Urban category, the South category is Banjarwangi District with 9 Pioneer Tourism Villages, the Central category is Cisurupan District with 6 Pioneer Tourism Villages, and the North category is Malangbong District with 9 Pioneer Tourism Villages.

No	Playing Field	Subdistrict	Village	Tourism Thema
1	Urban	TarogongKaler	Jati	Fishing Tourism
2	Urban	TarogongKaler	Mekarjaya	Mountain Tourism
3	Urban	TarogongKaler	Panjiwangi	Agro- Tourism
4	Urban	TarogongKaler	Pasawahan	Educational Tourism
5	Urban	TarogongKaler	Rancabango	HillTourism
6	Urban	TarogongKaler	Sukajadi	Village Tourism
7	Urban	TarogongKaler	Tanjung	Durian Garden Tourism

Based on the table, the government needs to play a role in developing tourist villages. Rural tourism has two basic features: it employs rural inhabitants, and involves recycling and revalorizing existing rural infrastructure and heritage resources as tourist accommodations and attractions (Yong 2021). However, based on the results of an interview with the Head of Pasawahan Village, the implementation of the pilot program for Tourist Villages still experiences several obstacles, including 1) the lack of socialization in the form of training or coaching to the community and managers in managing Tourist Villages, 2) the lack of budget in implementing Tourist Villages so that the facilities, both infrastructure and facilities of Tourist Villages are inadequate, 3) there are no regulations at the Regency level related to the implementation of Tourist Villages to provide direction or instructions in implementing the Tourist Village, and 4) the lack of promotion offered by Tourist Managers so that they have not been able to attract many enthusiasts.

Based on the background description above, the researcher is interested in conducting further research to find out how the implementation of Tourism Village in Pasawahan Village. This study aims to: 1) find out the implementation of Tourism Village in Pasawahan Village, TarogongKaler District, Garut Regency, 2) find out the factors that encourage the implementation of the program, 3) find out the inhibiting factors in the implementation of the Tourism Village program in TarogongKaler District, Garut Regency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

According to Siagian (inWarsono, Astuti, &Marom, 2019, hal. 5), administration is defined as the entire process of cooperation between two or more people based on certain rationality to achieve previously set goals. In the process of achieving these goals, government regulation in the form of public policy is very necessary.

Fredrickson (inRodiyahet al, 2021, page 63) defines public policy as anything proposed by a group of people or government in a particular environment that faces problems but has the opportunity to submit the proposal to achieve certain goals. An analysis of public policy implementation is needed to understand how public policy is implemented.

According to Van Meter and Van Horn (inWinarno, 2005, p. 102), policy implementation is an action taken by authorized parties to achieve the goals set in previous decisions. This implementation includes efforts to change decisions into real activities within a certain period and maintain efforts to achieve larger goals that existing strategies have not fully determined.

Furthermore, the theory of the concept of Tourism Village becomes important in this context. In Indonesia, there are four Tourism Village classifications: Pioneering, Developing, Advanced, and Independent. This classification is based on five main factors: the number of tourist visits, the creation of the tourism industry, the development of human capabilities and assets, the expansion of tourism products and services, and the availability of supporting infrastructure for the tourism industry. Based on the Tourism Village Guidelines, the Implementation of the Tourism Village Pioneer Program includes indicators of Attraction (offerings for tourists), Accessibility (ease of access for tourists), and Amenities (facilities supporting tourist needs), known as A3, as well as the development of Human Resources and involvement of the local community. There are the key features of a tourism livelihoods system which includes assets, tourism-related and non-tourism-related activities, outcomes, institutional arrangements and a vulnerability context.

Tourism Village will also create to develop many aspects, such as local businesses desire to providing better service and user experience. In addition, for a local business, it is an advantage to know statistics about market. In other side for visitors, the main purpose is having the best possible experience, avoiding congestion, and maintaining anonymity in the information collected (Flores-Crespo, Bermudez-Edo, and Garrido 2022) and government need to facilitate it all to increase economic and reduce poverty.

B. Methods

This study uses a qualitative-descriptive research method with a case study approach. In the analysis process, researchers collected primary data through observations and interviews conducted with several parties related to the implementation of the Tourism Village program in

Pasawahan Village, namely the Head of Pasawahan Village, the Head of Village-Owned Enterprise/BUMDes, and institutions involved in the implementation of the Tourism Village.

In addition to primary data, this study also collected secondary data, including literature, articles, journals, and information sources from websites relevant to the research topic. Documentary data, such as the profile of Pasawahan Village and books on the development of tourist villages published by Pasawahan Village, are also used to enrich the analysis.

Researchers select informants who have authority, knowledge, and direct involvement in implementing Tourism Villages. Key informants in this study were the Head of the Tourism Division of the Tourism and Culture Office, the Head of Pasawahan Village, the Head of PasawahanBUMDes, and members of the community involved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of West Java Provincial Regulation Number 2 of 2022 concerning Tourism Villages

Referring to Regional Regulation Number 02 of 2022 concerning Tourism Villages, the empowerment of Tourism Villages can be carried out through:

- a. fostering the governance of Tourism Villages;
- b. increasing the capacity of human resources and the creative economy of advanced Tourism Villages;
- c. fostering Tourism Attractions in Tourism Villages;
- d. improving and developing the marketing of Tourism Villages, and
- e. facilitating the development of business networks and partnerships.

To see how this Tourism Village pilot program is implemented, namely by looking at the indicators of attractions, accessibility, amenities and human resources as stated in the Tourism Village Guidelines.

2. Implementation of the Tourism Village Pilot Program in Pasawahan Village, TarogongKaler District.

Based on the results of observations on the implementation of the Tourism Village Pilot Program Policy in Pasawahan Village. The researcher analyzed the policy's implementation. There were several findings in the implementation of the policy. The following are the results of the researcher's observations related to the Implementation of the Tourism Village Pilot Program in Pasawahan Village, TarogongKaler District, Garut Regency, using the theory of Tourism Village Program Implementation according to Agnes Wirdayanti *et al*:

1). Attractions

Attractions or potential attractions, namely by looking at how to socialize potential to the community and how to pioneer infrastructure development in Eduwisata. To attract tourists, attractions are very essential. Three capital attractions attract tourists: natural resources, cultural tourism attractions, and artificial attractions. Tourism capital can develop into tourist attractions in the area where it is found. Attractions motivate someone to visit the tourist spot (Darmawan, 2019). Based on the observations in the field, the researcher

analyzed that in this attraction indicator, the management and the village government had difficulty pioneering the provision of infrastructure for Beekeeping Eduwisata. This is because the budget is limited, namely only from the Village Fund. However, the private sector, namely the Young Beekeeping Farmer Development Foundation and the Village Government, also continue to strive to socialize this program, marked by the implementation of the Village Deliberation and at the time of observation, many people were carrying out activities in Beekeeping Eduwisata such as building buildings for toilets, cleaning roads and others. So, the attraction indicator has been running and planned carefully, but its implementation is still not optimal.

In the pioneering of the Guntur Mountain Beekeeping Edutourism, each party has its respective functional duties following those stated in Regional Regulation Number 02 of 2022 concerning Tourism Villages. However, the intensity of the implementation of mentoring and socialization is not to the directions stated in the Regional Regulation. So, there needs to be improvement and re-socialization so that each line involved in this program can carry out each functional task determined in the Regulation.

2). Accessibility

Accessibility, the ease offered to enjoy tourism, is one of the indicators for the implementation of the Tourism Village pilot program in the Gunung Guntur Beekeeping Education. According to the Tourism Guidelines, accessibility is seen by improving the climate of the tourism village and roads. Based on documents and interview results from various parties, the researcher analyzed that there were several parties involved in the implementation of this program, including the Garut Regency Government, Disparbud, DPMD Garut Regency, Pasawahan Village Government, BUMDesSauyunanPasawahan Village, and the Young Beekeeping Farmers Development Foundation, and several private parties who have had other operational cooperation. Based on the results of observations in the field, the researcher analyzed that the accessibility indicator had been implemented but was not optimal due to difficulties in meeting supporting needs that required large costs, but the source of income used only came from Village Funds or the APBN. However, suppose you look at the preparation in the planning of the Tourism Village pilot. In that case, it has been very mature, marked by the implementation of the Village Deliberation and then cooperation with several private parties and BUMN to improve infrastructure in Beekeeping Education, so it can be concluded that in the accessibility indicator, the implementation of the Tourism Village pilot program has not been optimal.

3). Amenities

Amenities in tourism are in the form of supporting the fulfillment of needs to maintain the tidiness of the tourist village, such as the availability of lighting, clean water, telephone networks, worship accommodation, health, telecommunications, culinary, and parking lots. The village government continues to organize the Beekeeping Edutourism, from the provision of camps to other infrastructure. In the spatial planning for Beekeeping Edutourism, a rest area is also planned to be built, which is expected to attract many Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises/MSMEs involved in improving the economy of the residents of Pasawahan Village. In addition, several infrastructure facilities have been built, including bee houses, entrance gates, tourist writing monuments, huts, and roads. However,

the condition of the road has not been fully repaired and it is still a rocky road, so it is difficult to use for walking. In the amenity indicator, the implementation of the Tourism Village pilot is still not optimal.

4). Human Resources

Human Resources and the community are the indicators to see how the village tourism pilot program is implemented in the Gunung Guntur Beekeeping Edutourism, Pasawahan Village, TarogongKaler District, Garut Regency. The implementation is by seeing whether there has been an increase in human resources, either in the form of technical guidance or training related to the management of tourist attractions or improving the economy of residents around tourist attractions to advance tourism and the village economy. Training related to the Tourism Village was only carried out in 2022 as many as three times where the participants who attended were the Village Government, Tourism Village Managers, and the community. So, if the government intends to increase the knowledge and insight of the Beekeeping Edutourism managers, the number of training and mentoring is not optimal. In the implementation of the Village Tourism pilot program in Pasawahan Village, the Village Government strives to continue to inform the community to be involved in its implementation starting from its management or registering its MSMEs with Beekeeping Edutourism, but only 5 MSMEs are involved out of the 15 targets to be achieved.

In addition to information in the Musdes event, the Village and tourism managers also communicate through social media to attract public interest to be aware of tourism. So, in the human resources indicator, the community is still not ready for changes in its environment. However, on the one hand, the government and private sector continue to strive for the community to participate in managing and have a sense of ownership of the progress of Guntur Mountain Beekeeping Edutourism. There needs to be mentoring and socialization or re-training by involving more people, both those around the Edutourism and the general public of Pasawahan Village, TarogongKaler District so that community empowerment related to Tourism Village Management can cover the entire population of Pasawahan Village.

2. Obstacles to Implementing the Tourism Village Pilot Program

In the implementation of this Tourism Village pilot program, there are still several obstacles in its implementation. The researcher summarizes these obstacles as follows:

1. Limited budget for the arrangement of Beekeeping Edutourism;
2. Lack of public awareness to be involved in Edutourism;
3. Lack of intensity of the Regional Government to provide assistance and socialization related to Tourism Villages;
4. Community thinking has not yet accepted change and is still closed;
5. Lack of investors due to lack of promotion;
6. Edutourism has not been able to generate Original Local Government Revenue/PADes because there are no entrance tickets and Rest Areas.

CONCLUSION

From the implementation of the Gunung Guntur Beekeeping Edutourism Tourism Village pilot program in Pasawahan Village, TarogongKaler District, it can be concluded that the policy has been running but has not been optimal because it faces several obstacles. The analysis of the implementation of this program uses a theory based on the Village Tourism Guidelines with four main indicators as follows:

- 1. Attractions:** The Village and Regional Governments have carried out socialization regarding tourism potential and efforts to pioneer facilities and infrastructure. However, the amount of socialization, coaching, and assistance from the Regional Government for managers of Tourism Villages is still not intensive enough. As a result, the management of Tourism Villages has not been running optimally, so the existing potential has not been fully utilized.
- 2. Accessibility:** The Village Government and BUMDes prioritize infrastructure development in tourist locations to facilitate access for tourists. However, this effort is hampered by limited funds, most of which only come from Village Funds. The large cost of infrastructure development is still a major obstacle in increasing accessibility.
- 3. Amenities:** Amenities, which function to support the fulfillment of tourist needs and maintain the tidiness of the Tourism Village, are still inadequate. The existing facilities and infrastructure are not enough to support the improvement of the economy of residents. This indicates the need for further investment in facilities that can increase the comfort and attractiveness of tourists.
- 4. Human Resources and Community:** Efforts have been made to improve the quality of Human Resources (HR) through technical guidance and related training, but the results have not been optimal. The community is not fully prepared to face the changes brought by the Tourism Village program and still shows a lack of interest in being actively involved in tourism management. This indicates the need for more intensive efforts in community empowerment to ensure the sustainability of the Tourism Village program.

Overall, although the Gunung Guntur Beekeeping Edutourism Village program has been running, various aspects still need improvement. Increasing the intensity of mentoring, optimizing infrastructure, improving supporting facilities, and empowering the community are important steps that need to be taken to achieve the success and sustainability of this program in the future.

RECOMMENDATION

1 For the Author

It is expected that the author can broaden his insight and knowledge in analyzing various problems and can provide useful references for the wider community.

2) For the Garut Regency Tourism and Culture Office and Tourism Village Managers

It is expected that the Garut Regency Tourism and Culture Office can provide continuous assistance and socialization regarding the procedures for implementing Tourism Villages. In addition, derivative regulations are needed that provide clear guidelines for the village and managers in the implementation, including budget submission procedures. Tourism Village managers are also expected to be more active in seeking information and marketing Tourism Villages to attract investors, both in the form of CSR and investment from the private sector. In addition, coordination for implementing training and community empowerment needs to be improved so that more people are involved in managing Tourism Villages.

3) For Further Researchers

Further researchers are expected to be able to observe the existing conditions of implementing Tourism Villages in Pasawahan Village so that the data presented is the latest.

REFERENCES

- Abdal. (2015). *Kebijakan Publik (Memahami Konsep Kebijakan Publik)*. Bandung: UIN Sunan Gunung Djati.
- Agustino, L. (2008). *Dasar-Dasar Kebijakan Publik*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Dinas Pemberdayaan Masyarakat dan Desa. (2021). Keberadaan Badan Usaha Milik Desa Pariwisata Bidang Wisata Desa Berdasarkan Desa/Kelurahan di Jawa Barat.
- Flores-Crespo, Pedro, Maria Bermudez-Edo, and Jose Luis Garrido. 2022. "Smart Tourism in Villages: Challenges and the Alpujarra Case Study." *Procedia Computer Science* 204: 663–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.08.080>.
- Gao, Jing, and Bihu Wu. 2017. "Revitalizing Traditional Villages through Rural Tourism: A Case Study of Yuanjia Village, Shaanxi Province, China." *Tourism Management* 63: 223–33. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2017.04.003>.
- Hanapi. (2022, Januari 29). *Visit Garut*. Dipetik Maret 12, 2023, dari Visit Garut: <https://www.garutkab.go.id/news/pemkab-garut-siapkan-masterplan-desa-wisata>
- Iskandar. (2009). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Gaung Persada.
- Kreatif, P. M. (2021). *Paten No. 09*. Indonesia.
- Mardiah, Adha, R., & Kurniawan. (2019). Strategi Promosi Pariwisata Di Dinas Pariwisata Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Barat. *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Publik*, 07, 25-33.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, M. (1992). *Analisis Data Kualitatif*. Jakarta: Universitas Indonesia.
- Mulyana, Y., Huraerah, A., & Martiawan, R. (2019, Januari-Juni). Kebijakan Pengembangan Destinasi Pariwisata Cianjur Selatan di Kabupaten Cianjur Jawa Barat. *JISPO*, 9 No. 1, 491.
- Nailufar, N. N. (2020, Januari 9). *Desa*. Dipetik Maret 28, 2023, dari Desa: <https://www.kompas.com/skola/read/2020/01/09/130000569/desa-definisi-dan-unsurnya>
- Patience Nwokaego, A., & Ifeanyi Jude, O. (2022). Tourist Attractions And Economic Development In Nigeria: An Empirical Analysis. *GPH-International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 5(01), 69-79. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6966828>
- Peraturan Daerah Provinsi Jawa Barat. (2022). *Desa Wisata*. 9.
- Priasukmana, S. (2001). Pembangunan Desa Wisata Kepulauan Karimun Jawa. *Journal of Educational Social Studies*, 2 No. 1, 42-26.
- Satispi, E., & Mufidayaiti, K. (2019). *Buku Ajar Kebijakan Publik Teori dan Aplikasinya*. Jakarta: UMJ PRESS.
- Sesotyaningtyas, Mega, and Asnawi Manaf. 2015. "Analysis of Sustainable Tourism Village Development at Kutoharjo Village, Kendal Regency of Central Java." *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 184(August 2014): 273–80. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.05.091>.
- Sugiyono. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R & D*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- Tachan. (2008). *Implementasi Budaya Unggulan Di Industri Menuju World Class*. Jakarta: Menara Tunggal.
- Tim Penyusun. (2023). *Buku Panduan Skripsi Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik*. Garut: FISIP UNIGA. Vitasurya, Vincentia Reni. 2016. "Local Wisdom for Sustainable Development of Rural Tourism, Case on Kalibiru and Lopati Village, Province of Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta." *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 216(October 2015): 97–108.
- Warsono, H., Astuti, R. S., & Marom, A. (2019). *Buku Ajar Teori Administrasi*. Semarang: Departemen Administrasi Publik Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Politik Universitas Diponegoro.
- Winarno, B. (2005). *Teori dan Proses Kebijakan Publik*. Yogyakarta: Media Pressindo.
- Winarno, B. (2007). *Kebijakan Publik: Teori dan Proses Edisi Revisi*. Yogyakarta: Media Pressindo.

- Wirdayanti, A., Asri, A., Anggono, B. D., Hartoyo, D. R., Indarti, E., Gautama, H., et al. (2021). *Pedoman Desa Wisata*. Jakarta: Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Kemaritiman dan Investasi Republik Indonesia.
- Yoeti, A. O. (2007). *Perencanaan dan Pengembangan Pariwisata*. Jakarta: PT. Pradnya Paramita.
- Yong, Enn Lun. 2021. "Understanding the Economic Impacts of Sea-Level Rise on Tourism Prosperity: Conceptualization and Panel Data Evidence." *Advances in Climate Change Research* 12(2): 240–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accre.2021.03.009>.